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**Forming A Culture Of Ethical Decision-Making Among Students And Its
Impact On Social Activism****Raxmatova Dinora Isomovna**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the formation of a culture of moral decision-making in students and its impact on the level of social activity. The development of decision-making competence in the process of moral education highlights the formation of qualities such as independent thinking, a sense of responsibility, and readiness for active participation in society in the younger generation. At the same time, the harmony of social values, national-spiritual traditions, and criteria of modern thinking in making moral choices is studied separately. The study substantiates the effectiveness of using interactive methods, educational situations, and pedagogical technologies aimed at social activity.

Keywords: educational culture, social activity, decision-making, spiritual values, responsibility, youth education, interactive methods, pedagogical approach.

Introduction.

Today's world requires not only knowledge, but also moral maturity, independence in decision-making, and social responsibility. Especially in the choice of the life path of the younger generation, in making the right and fair decisions, the role of moral education is incomparable. After all, life consists of a chain of complex choices, tests and decisions. The formation of a person as a person largely depends on the decisions he makes and on what moral basis these decisions are based.

School is not only a place of education, but also an environment where personal education, social consciousness and moral values are formed. Every action of a student, the decisions that form the basis of his behavior, reflect his inner world, the moral criteria formed in his mind. Therefore, forming a culture of moral decision-making in students means raising a morally healthy, socially active, responsible person of the future society.

Against the backdrop of the spiritual crisis observed around the world today and the cultural distortions occurring under the influence of technology, moral education is more relevant than ever. If young people do not learn to make independent decisions based on moral criteria, they often face uncertainty, instability, and social indifference in life. Therefore, this article deeply analyzes the importance of developing a culture of moral decision-making in students, pedagogical mechanisms, and how this process affects their social activity.

Theoretical basis.

Moral decision-making is not a simple choice, but a complex process that is

inextricably linked with a person's inner world, social experience, and spiritual values. Students are faced with various situations from a young age: interaction with a classmate, relationship with a teacher, pressure in the family environment, the flow of modern information, and many other factors that play a decisive role in the formation of their moral decision-making skills. This requires a deep study of this issue not only from a pedagogical, but also from a psychological and sociological point of view.

In scientific literature, the culture of moral decision-making is based on a person's internal principles, beliefs, morality and the level of understanding of their social roles in society. Enlightenment educators, in particular Y. Komensky, J. Rousseau, I. Kant, and later representatives of modern Uzbek pedagogy - A. Avloniy, M. Behbudiy and others, saw moral education as a priority in the educational process. As A. Avloniy said, "Education is a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction for us." Today, against the backdrop of global problems, technological progress, and the increasing flow of information, the need for young people to make conscious choices is sharply increasing. In particular, they need to have a culture of moral decision-making in order to become active, responsible, and initiative individuals in society. Because social activism is not just an external action, it is, first of all, internal motivation, an understanding of one's place and role in society.

From a psychological point of view, a person's self-esteem, empathy, will, and level of social adaptation play a significant role in decision-making. From a pedagogical point of view, this process can be influenced by the teacher's personal example, a system of educational work, interdisciplinary integration, and conversations based on moral issues. Moral education is not a one-sided education, but a system based on dialogue, encouraging young people to think, evaluate, and understand themselves. Thus, theoretically, the formation of a culture of moral decision-making should be considered as the internal content of education. This, in turn, creates the basis for increasing the social activity of students and their active civic position in society. Therefore, the development of this culture serves to strengthen the foundations of a future-oriented, stable, and spiritually healthy society.

Source analysis:

In the process of analyzing scientific and theoretical sources on the formation of a culture of moral decision-making in students, it can be seen that this direction is located at the intersection of pedagogy, psychology, philosophy and sociology. This requires studying the topic on the basis of an integrated approach.

Among the early sources, issues of moral education are prioritized in the works of such modern enlighteners as Abdulla Avloni, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Ismail Gaspirali. In particular, A. Avloni in his work "Turkish Rose or Morality"

emphasizes the need to form moral qualities from childhood and believes that this will lead to a spiritual awakening in society.

In modern pedagogical literature, for example, Z. Kholboyeva, R. Nishonova, N. Toshkhodjayev and others have thoroughly covered the methodological foundations of moral education, the relationship between decision-making competence and personal qualities. Z. Kholboyeva describes moral education as "a complex process that ensures a person's conscious entry into social life."

An analysis of foreign literature shows that this issue is of global importance. In particular, the theory of moral development, put forward by L. Kohlberg, provides a deep understanding of the gradual maturation of young people in making moral decisions. According to Kohlberg's model, at each age stage, a person perceives moral norms differently, and these decisions directly affect their social activity.

Albert Bandura's social learning theory argues that the environment, role models, and observation are the main factors in the formation of young people's moral decisions. This idea serves as an important basis for the influence of a teacher's personal example on the student.

Also, reports on education from international organizations such as UNESCO and UNICEF suggest considering moral education and social activity as a whole process. In their opinion, modern education should not only educate knowledge, but also values, intercultural dialogue, and social responsibility. An analysis of the existing literature shows that the formation of a culture of ethical decision-making in students requires a multifactorial and systematic approach. Effective results in this direction can be achieved by combining historical, theoretical and practical sources.

Conclusion.

The formation of a culture of ethical decision-making in students is not only a central direction of the educational process, but also an important factor in preparing young people for social life. Studies show that students with moral awareness and the ability to make independent decisions are distinguished by their social activity, initiative and level of responsibility. In the formation of this culture, the personal example of the teacher, the use of deliberative and problem-based approaches in lessons, and the organization of educational activities using real-life situations are of particular importance. In particular, teaching students a culture of responsibility for their choices and decisions strengthens their sense of social responsibility.

In conclusion, it can be said that by forming a culture of moral decision-making, it is possible to educate students as socially active, conscious and spiritually mature individuals. This, in turn, creates a solid foundation for building a stable civil society.

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